

EMODnet

European Marine
Observation and
Data Network

EMODnet Physics

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METADATA Format Specifications

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Introduction

The European Marine Observation and Data Network, EMODnet, is a long-term marine initiative implementing mechanism of the European Commission's Marine Knowledge 2020 strategy^{2,3} to unlock the potential of Europe's wealth of marine data. Based on the principle of collecting data once and using it many times for many purposes, EMODnet is a network of organizations supported by the EU's Integrated Maritime Policy⁶ linked by a data management structure. These organizations work together to facilitate the discovery and access to marine data and data products representing the following seven main themes: bathymetry, biology, chemistry, geology, human activities, physics, and seabed habitats. EMODnet provides a gateway to those marine data accompanied by their metadata and data products through a number of thematic portals and a central portal (www.emodnet.eu).

EMODnet Physics (www.emodnet-physics.eu) is one of the seven domain-specific projects that through the effort done under the ur-EMODnet preparatory action (MARE/2010/02) and successive development (MARE/2012/10; EASME/EMFF/2016/006) and operational (EASME/2019/OP/0003) phases have been successful in designing, organizing and running operational services where ocean physics data and data products built with common standards can be found, viewed and downloaded in a way that is free of charge and free of restrictions of use.

The EMODnet Physics originates from the advances made by the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) community - especially the European component (EuroGOOS) - in the development of physical operational oceanography capabilities. The consortium represents a strong cooperation between Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring System (CMEMS) In Situ Thematic Centre (INSTAC) SeaDataNet network of NODCs, International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES), and Joint Technical Commission for Oceanography and Marine Meteorology in situ Observations Programme Support centre (JCOMMOPS).

EMODnet Physics unlocks, links, aggregates, and makes available ocean physics parameters and available themes are temperature of the water column, salinity of the water column, horizontal velocity of the water column, changes in sea level and sea level trends, wave height and period, wind speed and atmospheric pressure, water clarity (light attenuation), underwater sound (noise), inflow from rivers, and sea-ice coverage. Time series, profiles, and sampled datasets are made available, as recorded by fixed platforms (moorings, tide gauges, HF radars, etc.), moving platforms (ARGO, Lagrangian buoys, ferryboxes, etc.) and repeated observations (CTDs, etc.). Available products are collections of in situ data, reanalysis and trends from in situ data, elaboration in space and/or time of in situ data and model output for a given parameter.

Data from EMODnet Physics European pillar repositories and infrastructures, i.e. CMEMS-INSTAC and SDN-NODC, are integrated with other available sources such as ICES, PANGAEA, PSMSL, SONEL, IOC, IOOS, IMOS, etc. to make available the most comprehensive ocean physics catalogues.

To this end EMODnet Physics is undertaking continuous developments and updates and integrates, adapts and contributes to the evolution of common standards and procedures.

This document describes the EMODnet Physics Metadata format.

² European Commission (2010). Marine Knowledge 2020 Marine Data and Observation for Smart and Sustainable Growth. Commission Communication COM (2010) 461, Publications Office of the European Union.

³ European Commission (2012). Marine Knowledge 2020 from Seabed Mapping to Ocean Forecasting. Green Paper, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.

EMODnet Physics data disclaimer.

Data are published without any warranty, express or implied. The user assumes all risk arising from his/her use of published data. Data are intended to be the best available version as provided by sources or integrators, data include estimates of data quality and accuracy, anyhow these estimates or the data themselves may contain errors. It is responsibility of the user to assess if the data are appropriate for his/her use, and to interpret the data, data quality, and data accuracy accordingly.

Metadata definition

Metadata is "data that provides information about other data"

Metadata describes a broad range of information that allows observations to be understood and evolved into information and knowledge. It provides a context for research findings, ideally in a machine-readable format and it is used by users to understand if data matches with its expectations. Metadata requires the use of standardized sets of terms to solve problem with ambiguities

The collection and management of marine data metadata is a complex step-wise process that include identification of the observing requirements/sensors, the configuration of the sensors, the deployment at sea and collection of the observation that are regularly transmitted to a shore-side receiving station. The receiving station reformats the data messages, possibly applying some automated quality control, and then distributes the data over one of several communication pathways like the Global Telecommunication System (GTS). Data Assembly Centers collect these data and develop added value reanalysis/products. Each step produces information that may be associated to the given observation, hence generating an immense volume of metadata information.

EMODnet Physics is an integrating and discovery infrastructure and EMODnet Physics metadata are primarily designed to provide user with information that identifies a collection of files as a thematic/coherent data set, supports discovery of that collection using keyword/spatial/temporal searches, gives information of/links to the processing history of the observations (source, version, quality assessment and control) and provides links to document sensors and platform characteristics associated with the observation.

If we refer to the ISO standards for cataloguing the information the key references are:

- ISO 8601 Representation of date and time
- ISO 19108 Temporal characteristics of geographic information
- ISO 19113 revised by 19157 standards for geographic information
- ISO 19115 Geographical information metadata
- ISO 19119 Taxonomy of services
- ISO 19139 Geographical information metadata implementation specification

ISO 19113 defines quality principles, which are applied in ISO 19115 (geographic metadata). The metadata records in the current GEOSS use the ISO 19115 data model and its companion XML encoding (ISO 19139). ISO 19115 Standard requires a basic minimum number of metadata elements that are essential for the data presentation:

- Dataset or dataset series on specific challenges ('what'),
- Geographic bounding box ('where'),
- Temporal extent ('when'),
- Contact point to learn more about or order the dataset ('who').

Obviously, additional elements increase interoperability and usability.

The adoption of ISO standards and the use of shared controlled vocabularies are a key prerequisite towards consistency and interoperability.

Controlled vocabularies consist of lists of standardized terms that cover a broad spectrum of disciplines of relevance to the oceanographic and wider community, and a key outcome of past ICES/IOC Study Group on the Development of Marine Data Exchange Systems was the establishment of a combined SeaDataNet and MarineXML Vocabulary Content Governance Group (SeaVoX). This set of common standards for the marine domain is updated and maintained by SeaDataNet partners.

EMODnet Physics adopted many of the SeaDataNet common vocabularies and directories, and integrates additional metadata elements which are of particular use for the marine data community to have marine data findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable. Examples are the use of Climate and Forecasting conventions for parameters that are mapped versus the NVS P01-P02 or the adoption of CMEMS INSTAC convention and recommendations for unique platform identification. Each platform in the CMEMS INSTAC has a unique code that, when available, is the WMO (World Maritime Organization) code. JCOMMOPS (as the focal point for the practical coordination of the in-situ ocean observing systems defined by JCOMM) also has a key role in the overall management of the platforms and programs metadata.

Data collection and dissemination

1.1 Data collection

EMODnet Physics develops a common procedure to access ocean physics parameters and products from several sources: available products are collections of in situ data, reanalysis and trends from in situ data, elaboration in space and/or time of in situ data and model output for a given parameter. Data products time age ranges from real-time, near real time to validated long term time series.

The synchronization process is based on smart adapters that connect data from sources to the system (Figure 1), and apply procedures to harmonize information (common standards, common vocabularies, complete and integrate metadata). At the end of the process data is ready for the dissemination through the EMODnet Physics dissemination channels/catalogues (i.e. mapviewer, ERDDAP, TDS, GeoServer, GeoNetwork catalogue)⁴.

Figure 1. Data management flow in EMODnet Physics

Real-time data acquisition and dissemination is based on the latest implementation of the Sensor Web Enablement (SWE) and Sensor Observation Service (SOS) standards. These interoperable interfaces permit the insertion and retrieval of georeferenced observation data in a standardized format. This new data stream management is done jointly, in collaboration with EMODnet Data Ingestion, and besides developing and deploying the SOS, the two projects are working and contributing on a set of standards to implement ISO/OGC O&M features and SensorML for the Marine domain⁵. The acquisition of near real-time physical parameters is largely an automated process: EMODnet Physics collects data from a network of providers and integrators (CMEMS INSTAC, global and regional assembly centers, regional ocean observing Systems, etc.) and organizes products in the EMODnet Physics ERDDAP and hence in the map viewer. Typically, the transport format is NetCDF (CF Convention), as defined by the EuroGOOS DATAMEQ working group and the SeaDataNet technical working team, and includes metadata and data quality flags. Data quality is flagged according to an automatic – unsupervised procedure at the data source. EMODnet Physics is operationally processing this data flow to generate map layers (organized in the EMODnet GeoServer) and extract in situ (monthly) trends, averages and peak values of the parameters. Historical validated datasets are organized in collaboration with SeaDataNet and its network of National Oceanographic Data Centers, which are supplying EMODnet Physics with products

⁴ erddap.emodnet-physics.eu, thredds.emodnet-physics.eu, geoserver.emodnet-physics.eu, map.emodnet-physics.eu, catalogue.emodnet-physics.eu

⁵ <https://odip.github.io/MarineProfilesForSWE/>

(climatology) on temperature and salinity of the water column. EMODnet Physics is also acting as in situ historical data collection broker between users and the NODCs. For the historical validated datasets (fixed stations – mooring, tide gauge) the metadata format is the CDIs (common data index) and the transport formats are ODV4 and NetCDF (CF convention). For the parameters (and platforms) that are not managed by its pillars (e.g. river outflow, water noise, sea surface currents as recorded by HF radars, etc.), EMODnet Physics is supporting, promoting and contributing to development of the data management chain by applying common standards and procedures. Other aggregated and validated thematic collections/products (e.g. PSMSL, SONEL, SOCAT, etc.) are linked and ingested from sources (according the indication of the product principal investigator) by means of specific smart connectors.

1.2 Data Sources

EMODnet Physics develops an ocean data information system based on a federated network of sources. These sources may be marine data integrators, marine data repositories, ocean observation programs, data assembly centers, marine institutes, oceanographic data centers, etc. The main (not exhaustive) list of sources is:

- CMEMS INSTAC (in situ measurement from EuroGOOS and ROOSs institutes)
- European Marine Institutes and National Oceanographic Data Centers (see annex)
- SeaDataNet (CDI and Climatology)
- GDAC (Coriolis)
- Global Sea Level Observing System (GLOSS)
- IOC Sea Level Station Monitoring (SLS)
- Permanent service for mean sea level (PSMSL)
- University of Hawaii Sea Level Center (UHSLC) - GLOSS Fast-Delivery Center
- Système d'Observation du Niveau des Eaux Littorales (SONEL)
- International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES)
- Deep Ocean Multi-Disciplinary Ocean Reference Stations (OceanSITES)
- ARGO profiling float data
- Southern Oceans Observing System (SOOS)
- Global HF Radar Network
- Everyone's Gliding Observatories (EGO) and OceanGlider Network
- Marine Mammals Exploring the Oceans Pole to Pole (MEOP)
- Voluntary Observing Ship (VOS), Ship Of Opportunity Program (SOOP)
- Data Buoy Cooperation Panel (DBCP), Arctic Buoy Data (IAPB),
- Tropical Moored buoys: Pacific Ocean (TAO, TRITON), Atlantic Ocean (PIRATA), Indian Ocean (RAMA)
- PANGAEA - Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science
- European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory (EMSO)
- Global Ocean Surface Underway Data Pilot Project (GOSUD)
- US National Data Buoy Center (NDBC), Integrated Ocean Observing System (IOOS), National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA)
- Australian Integrated Marine Observing System (IMOS)
- Global Ocean Ship-Based Hydrographic Investigations Program (GO-SHIP)
- Global Ocean Data Analysis Project (GLODAP)
- Surface Ocean CO₂ Atlas (SOCAT)

1.3 Data processing

EMODnet Physics provides the user with information about the quality of data and link to the applied quality check procedure. In general, if data is real-time and near-real time data, the quality control procedure is automatic or semi-automatic. If data is a reanalysis/long term series, the quality control procedure involves thematic expertise and supervision. Quality check procedures include consistency controls on time, location, range-spike, etc. and attach a Quality Flag to data. The QC/QF method is defined according to the observation

platform, the sensor type and the parameter. Whenever possible EuroGOOS⁶ and SeaDataNet⁷ recommendations are applied as close as possible to data origin.

Table 1. QC/QF

Code Meaning Comment		
0	No QC was performed	-
1	Good data	All real-time QC tests passed.
2	Probably good data	These data should be used with caution
3	Bad data that are potentially correctable	These data are not to be used without scientific correction.
4	Bad data	Data have failed one or more of the tests.
5	Value changed	Data may be recovered after transmission error.
6	Not used	-
7	Nominal value	Data were not observed but reported.
		Example: an instrument target depth.
8	Interpolated value	Missing data may be interpolated from neighboring data in space or time.
9	Missing value	The value is missing, is not reported, is not applicable...

1.4 Data publishing and Data dissemination channels

EMODnet Physics develops and exploits different technologies and dissemination channels:

- ERDDAP - that implements FGDC Web Accessible Folder (WAF) with FGDC-STD-001-1998 and ISO 19115 WAF with ISO 19115-2/19139;
- THREDDS - that implements OpenDAP, NetCDF Subset Service, WCS 1.0 Service, WMS 1.3.0 Service, ncISO: Dataset Metadata Services, OAI Metadata harvesting;
- GeoServer that implements several Open Geospatial Consortium protocols including Web Map Service (WMS), Web Feature Service (WFS), Web Coverage Service (WCS) and Web Map Tile Service (WMTS) and that was lately updated with the INSPIRE module;
- GeoNetwork that implements WxS, OGC, ISO standards.
- web APIs, and web widgets

EMODnet Physics adopted ERDDAP as the core solution for data management and interoperability. ERDDAP supports both human interaction (e.g. OPeNDAP requests) and machine-to-machine interoperability. ERDDAP data server supports of several common data file formats (html table, netcdf, csv, txt, mat, json, etc.) and output files are created on-the-fly in any of this format. ERDDAP is free and open source code (JAVA program and source code is available in GitHub⁸) that uses Apache compatible software licenses.

Next section is presenting the EMODnet Physics Metadata Specifications as implemented in the EMODnet Physics ERDDAP data server.

⁶ <https://archimer.ifremer.fr/doc/00251/36230/34790.pdf>

⁷ https://www.seadatanet.org/content/download/596/file/SeaDataNet_QC_procedures_V2_%28May_2010%29.pdf

⁸ <https://github.com/BobSimons>

Data Format Reference

EMODnet Physics supports several data formats, ranging from csv, odv4, to netcdf. If the source is not implanting an ERDDAP data server to be linked to EMODnet Physics infrastructure (ERDDAP overcomes the main data format interoperability problems), in order to facilitate the ingestion/link process, it is recommended to use the Climate and Forecast convention NetCDF format version 4.

The CF metadata conventions (<https://cf-trac.llnl.gov/trac>) are designed to promote the processing and sharing of files created with the NetCDF API. The conventions define metadata that provide a definitive description of what the data in each variable represents, and the spatial and temporal properties of the data. This enables users of data from different sources to decide which quantities are comparable, and facilitates building applications with powerful extraction, regridding, and display capabilities. The standard is both mature and well-supported by formal governance for its further development. The standard is fully documented by a PDF manual accessible from a link from the CF metadata homepage (<https://cf-trac.llnl.gov/trac>). Note that CF is a developing standard and the current version is CF-1.6.

The European marine data infrastructures are based on the format of the files that are used to distribute OceanSITES data. Both CMEMS-INSTAC and SeaDataNet have developed some extensions to provide the user with more information. EMODnet Physics supports and recommends to include as many descriptive attributes as possible.

The EMODnet Physics Metadata format is based on an extension of the mandatory global attributes that are common between these three infrastructures. The "References and readings" section provides links to these data format reference manuals.

EMODnet Physics Metadata specifications

The EMODnet Physics Metadata covers three main categories. Some metadata are harvested from the source, some are mapped by common vocabularies and standards, some are fixed.

1.1 Discovery and Identification

This section describes the contents of the file overall and allows for data discovery, fields are human-readable and use units that are easy to understand. Some fields are lists and provide the user with inner information.

1.2 Conventions

This section indicates the adopted convention and language to describe information. It also includes the GEMET-INSPIRE theme.

1.3 Spatial and temporal dimension

The latitude and longitude datum are WGS84. EMODnet Physics uses the EPSG 4326 coordinate reference system to describe geographical positions, and uses ISO8601 for time.

Table 2. EMODnet Physics Metadata Specifications

GROUP	Metadata name	Occurrence	Level2	Vocabulary	Description	Example
Discovery and identification						
	ep_platformID	1			It should be the unique Identifier for EMODnet Physics	If the platform has a WMO code it should be the WMO code, if the platform run missions, it should be WMO-mission ID
	ep_DataID	1			ID for Data (internal ref to link EMODnet platformid and its dataset)	
	ep_platformCode	1			EMODnet Physics platform code (could be the WMO)	
	ep_platformName	1			EMODnet Physics platform name when available or WMO	
	ep_platformType	1		ep.platformType	CMEMS INSTAC/EMODnet Physics Platform short name	e.g. GL = glider, DB = drifting buoy
	sdn_platformType_L06	0-1		http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06/current/	SDN platform categories	SDN:L06::42
	ep_dataOwner	0-1		ep.dataOwner	Data owner full name	e.g. "ETT"
	sdn_dataOwner_EDMO	0-1		https://edmo.seadatanet.org/	SDN Data Owner EUROPEAN DIRECTORY OF MARINE ORGANISATIONS	e.g. "2764" is ETT
	ep_dataFeatureType	1-Many	ep_dataType	OceanSITES	Typology of data: timeseries, profile, trajectory	
	ep_parameterGroups	1-Many	ep_parameterGroup	CF long name	Observed Ocean feature	[Water Salinity,]
	ep_parameters	1-Many	ep_parameter	CF Terms	Observed Ocean feature	[PSAL]

The European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) is financed by the European Union under Regulation (EU) No 508/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 May 2014 on the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund.

	sdn_parameterGroups_P02	0-Many	sdn_parameterGroup_P02	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P02/current/	Observed features described by SDN parameter group vocabulary	[SDN:P02::PSAL, SDN:P02::ASLV]
	sdn_parameters_P01	0-Many	sdn_parameter_P01	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01/current/	Observed features described by SDN parameter (narrow) vocabulary	[SDN:P01::PSLTZZ01, SDN:P01::ASLVZZ01]
	ep_institution	0-1		ep.institution	Long name of the institution managing (hosting and disseminating) data	ETT
	sdn_institution_EDMO	0-1		https://edmo.seadatanet.org/	SDN Institution EUROPEAN DIRECTORY OF MARINE ORGANISATIONS	2764
	ep_institution_link	0-1		[http://link.eu/]	Link to the institution web site	www.ettsolutions.com
	ep_istitution_country	1		ISO3166		380
	ep_dataAssemblyCenter	0-1			Global/Regional/Thematic Data Assembly Center	e.g. Coriolis
	ep_principalInvestigator	0-1			Principal Investigator	e.g. Marco Alba
	ep_projects	0-Many	ep_project	ep.projects	Name of the project/observation program	[PSMSL,IOC]
	sdn_EDMERP	0-1		https://edmerp.seadatanet.org/	SDN EUROPEAN DIRECTORY OF MARINE ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH PROJECTS	7703
	sdn_platformCode	0-1		http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/C17/current/		xxxxx

	wmo_platformCode	0-1				99999
	sources	0-Many	sourcename		Name of the source of data	
			sourceplatformcode		Platform code from source	
			sourcelink		Source link	
			doi		Source DOI	
			sensorML		SensorML from source	
			quality doc - ref		Quality document from source	
	ep_namingAuthority	1		Fixed Value		EMODnet Physics
	ep_creatorName	1		Fixed Value		EMODnet Physics
	ep_creatorType	1		Fixed Value		Institution
	ep_creator_email	1		Fixed Value		contact@emodnet-physics.eu
	ep_contacts	1		Fixed Value		contact@emodnet-physics.eu
	ep_creatorUrl	1		Fixed Value		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/
	ep_comments	1		Fixed Value		
	ep_citation	1		Fixed Value		Data used in this [type of derived work: e.g. publication/report/model/map...] was collected from EMODnet Physics, www.emodnet-physics.eu/map , funded by the European Commission Directorate General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries [EASME/EMFF/2018/Lot3/SI2.810790]. Data are the property of the

						producer/owner. EMODnet Physics and the partners are not responsible for improper use.
	ep_distributionStatement	1		Fixed Value		EMODnet Physics and data originators strive to provide access to data with the highest quality available, but the user must be aware that the quality of the different datasets can vary considerably. Users should also take note that all portals are still under development so some features may not be complete and new datasets, parameters and tools are made available regularly. For instance, estimates of data quality are progressively being incorporated along with the datasets, but it is the responsibility of the user to assess the adequacy of those data

						for his/her particular work purposes: neither EMODnet Physics nor the data originators are liable for any negative consequences following direct or indirect use of EMODnet portal information, services, products and/or data.
	ep_platformPageLink	1			Link to EMODnet Physics Platform Page	https://emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=989003
	ep_dataLink	1-Many	dataID			123
			parameter		Parameter	SLEV
			link		Link to data	
			source		name of the data source	PSMSL
Conventions						
	data_character_set	1		Fixed Value	character set of metadata	utf8
	data_language	1		Fixed Value	data language of metadata	eng
	reference_system	1		https://epsg.io/	referenxe system of platform data	EPSG:4326
	references	0-Many	reference			
	GEMET-INSPIRE themes	0-Many	GEMET-INSPIRE theme	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P22/current/	Groupings of spatial data according to Annex I, II and III of the INSPIRE Directive [DS-D2.5]	SDN:P22::28
Geo-spatial-temporal						
	geospatial_lat_max	1		EPSG 4326		
	geospatial_lat_min	1		EPSG 4326		

geospatial_lat_units	1		Fixed Value	Fixed Value	degrees_north
geospatial_lon_max	1		EPSG 4326		
geospatial_lon_min	1		EPSG 4326		
geospatial_lon_units	1		Fixed Value	Fixed Value	degrees_east
geospatial_vertical_max	0-1				
geospatial_vertical_min	0-1				
geospatial_vertical_positive	0-1		Fixed Value	Fixed Value	down
geospatial_vertical_units	0-1		Fixed Value	Fixed Value	m
last_date_observation	1		ISO8601		
last_latitude_observation	1		EPSG 4326		
last_longitude_observation	1		EPSG 4326		
time_coverage_end	1		ISO8601		
time_coverage_start	1		ISO8601		
update_interval	0-1				
ep_seaRegions	0-Many	ep_seaRegion	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/C19/current/		[SDN:C19::3_1_1_5]
available_years	0-Many			List of year with data	
available_months	0-Many			List of month-year with data	
depths	0-Many			List of available depths	

	position_history	0-1			link to history of platform position (only for non-fixed platform)	
	geometry_type	1		ep.geometryType	Type of geometry (point,polyline, polygon)	point
Extra						
	ext_documentation				extra documentation fpor the platform	
	ext_info				extra info for the platform	
Versioning						
	version	0-1			versione number	
	previousVersion	0-1				
	changetime	0-1			varsion change datetime	
	trackchange	0-1			change from previous version	

Table 3. Mapping of CF names vs SDN:P0x

Group name	Code	CF StandardName	Extendend name	Unit	SDN	Current Code
Water Temperature	TEMP	sea_water_temperature	sea temperature	degree_Celsius	SDN:P01::TEMPPR01	
Water Temperature	POTENTIAL_TEMP	sea_water_potential_temperature	sea potential temperature	degree_Celsius	SDN:P02::TEMP	
Water Temperature	SSJT		sea temperature from tsg	degree_Celsius	SDN:P01::TEMPSG01	
Water Temperature	TEMP_IR_UNCOR_MEAN	sea_surface_skin_temperature	Skin temperature	degree_Celsius		
Water Temperature	TEMP_CTD_MEAN	sea_water_temperature	Seawater temperature CTD	degree_Celsius		
Water Temperature	TEMP_O2_RBR_MEAN	sea_water_temperature	Seawater temperature RBR	degree_Celsius		
Water Temperature	TEMP_O2_AANDERAA_MEAN	sea_water_temperature	Seawater temperature AANDERAA	degree_Celsius		
Water Temperature	TEMP_IR_SEA_HULL_UNCOMP_MEAN	sea_surface_skin_temperature	Hull Sea IR Temperature	degree_Celsius		
Water Temperature	TEMP_IR_SEA_WING_UNCOMP_MEAN	sea_surface_skin_temperature	Wing Sea IR Temperature	degree_Celsius		
Water Temperature	TEMP_CTD_RBR_MEAN	sea_water_temperature	Seawater temperature RBR CTD	degree_Celsius		
Water salinity	PSAL	sea_water_salinity	practical salinity	psu	SDN:P01::PSLTZZ01	
Water salinity	SSAL		salinity (pre-1978 definition)	g/kg		PSAL

Water salinity	USAL		undefined salinity	unknown		
Water salinity	ASAL	sea_water_absolute_salinity	absolute salinity	g/kg	SDN:P02::PSAL	
Water salinity	SAL_MEAN	sea_water_practical_salinity	Seawater salinity	psu		
Water salinity	SAL_RBR_MEAN	sea_water_practical_salinity	Seawater salinity RBR	psu		
Currents	CDIR	direction_of_sea_water_velocity				
Currents	HCSP	sea_water_speed	horizontal current speed	meter/second	SDN:P01::LCSAZZ01	
Currents	RFVL	sea_water_speed	Horizontal velocity of the water column (currents)	m/s	SDN:P02::RFVL	
Currents	CSPD	sea_water_speed				
Currents	EWCT	eastward_sea_water_velocity	west-east current component	meter/second	SDN:P01::LCEWZZ01	
Currents	NSCT	northward_sea_water_velocity	south-north current component	meter/second	SDN:P01::LCNSZZ01	
Currents	UCUR	eastward_sea_water_velocity				
Currents	VCUR	northward_sea_water_velocity				
Currents	HCDT	direction_of_sea_water_velocity	current to direction relative true north	degree	SDN:P01::LCDAZZ01	
Currents	VCSP	upward_sea_water_velocity	bottom-top current component	meter/second	SDN:P01::LRZAZZZZ	
Currents	RDVA	radial_sea_water_velocity_away_from_instrument	Radial sea water velocity away from instrument	m/s		

Currents	DRVA	direction_of_radial_vector_away_from_instrument	Direction of radial vector away from instrument	degree_true		
Optical Properties	LGCR					
Optical Properties	LERR					
Optical Properties	LRZA		vertical velocity of the water column (currents)		SDN:P01::LRZAZZZZ	
Optical Properties	BACKSCATTERING		backscattering	m-1 sr-1		
Optical Properties	LGH4	surface_downwelling_synthetic_photon_flux_in_air	light irradiance surface par	Micromol photon/(m2.s)	SDN:P01::PARERXSD	
Optical Properties	LINC	surface_downwelling_longwave_flux_in_air	long-wave incoming radiation	watt/m2	SDN:P01::LWRDZZ01	
Optical Properties	RDIN	surface_downwelling_radiative_flux_in_sea_water	incident radiation	watt/m2	SDN:P01:TLRDZZ01	
Optical Properties	SCATTERING		scattering	m-1 sr-1		
Optical Properties	TRANSMISSIVITY		transmissivity	per meter		
Optical Properties	TUR2		light attenuation coefficient	m-1	SDN:P01::ATTNZZ01	
Optical Properties	TUR3		light transmission	percent	SDN:P01::POPTZZ01	

Optical Properties	TUR5		turbidity	relative unit		
Optical Properties	TUR6		turbidity	milliF.T.U Formaz Turb Unit	SDN:P01::TURBXXXX	
Optical Properties	LGHT	downwelling_photosynthetic_photon_flux_in_sea_water	light irradiance immersed par	mE/m2/s		
Optical Properties	PAR_AIR_MEAN	surface_downwelling_photosynthetic_photon_flux_in_air	Surface Downwelling Photosynthetic Photon Flux In Air	mmol s-1 m-2		
Sea Level	SLEV	water_surface_height_above_reference_datum	observed sea level	meter	SDN:P01::ASLVZZ01	
Sea Level	ASLV	sea_level	sea level			SLEV
Sea Level	PREX				SDN:P02::PREX	
Sea Level	SLVR	sea_surface_height_correction_due_to_air_pressure_and_wind_at_high_frequency	residual sea level (observed - predicted)	meter	SDN:P01::ASLVR101	
Sea Level	SLEVD1	sea_surface_height_above_sea_level_demerliac_filter	observed sea level - Demerliac Filter	millimeter		SLEV
Sea Level	SLEVD2	sea_surface_height_above_sea_level_doodson_filter	observed sea level - Doodson Filter	millimeter		SLEV
Sea Level	DENS	sea_water_sigma_theta	Sea density (sigma-theta)	kg/m3		
Atmospheric	GWDR		wave direction		DN:P01::GWDRZZ01	
Atmospheric	ATTN	WC_Trans	transmittance and attenuation of the water column		SDN:P02::ATTN	

Atmospheric	RELH	relative_humidity	relative humidity	%	SDN:P01::CRELZZ01	
Atmospheric	ATMP	air_pressure	atmospheric pressure at altitude	hectopascal	SDN:P01::CAPHZZ01	
Atmospheric	ATMS	air_pressure_at_sea_level	atmospheric pressure at sea level	hectopascal	SDN:P01::CAPAZZ01	
Atmospheric	ATPT	tendency_of_air_pressure	atmospheric pressure hourly tendency	hectopascal/hour	SDN:P01::APRESSTN	
Atmospheric	DRYT	air_temperature	air temperature in dry bulb	degree_Celsius	SDN:P01::CTMPZZ01	
Atmospheric	PRRD	lwe_precipitation_rate	daily precipitation rate	millimeter/day	SDN:P01::CPRRRG01	
Atmospheric	PRRT	lwe_precipitation_rate	hourly precipitation rate	millimeter/hour	SDN:P01::CPRRRG01	
Atmospheric	BARO_PRES_MEAN	air_pressure_at_sea_level	atmospheric pressure at sea level	hectopascal		
Atmospheric	TEMP_AIR_MEAN	air_temperature	air temperature in dry bulb	degree_Celsius		
Atmospheric	RH_MEAN	relative_humidity	relative humidity	%		
Atmospheric	RH1	relative_humidity	relative humidity - port sensor	%		
Atmospheric	RH2	relative_humidity	relative humidity - starboard sensor	%		
Atmospheric	TA1	air_temperature	air temperature in dry bulb - port sensor	degree_Celsius		
Atmospheric	TA2	air_temperature	air temperature in dry bulb - starboard sensor	degree_Celsius		

Atmospheric	PA1_Pa	air_pressure	atmospheric pressure at altitude - port sensor	hectopascal		
Atmospheric	PA2_Pa	air_pressure	atmospheric pressure at altitude - starboard sensor	hectopascal		
Atmospheric	SINC	surface_downwelling_shortwave_flux_in_air	Shortwave/solar incoming radiation	W/m2		
Atmospheric	NRAD	surface_net_downward_radiative_flux	Net total incoming radiation	W/m2		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CNDC	sea_water_electrical_conductivity	electrical conductivity	S/m	SDN:P01::CNDCZZ01	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	FLU2	mass_concentration_of_chlorophyll_a_fluorescence_in_sea_water	fluorescence	milligram/m3	SDN:P01::CPHLP01	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	KRTS					
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	HEAV	vertical_displacement	vertical displacement (heave)		SDN:P01::HEAVZZZZ	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	EWSB		wind strength and direction		SDN:P02::EWSB	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	PSST					

Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	PTDZ					
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	TCNT					
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	OPBS	optical_backscattering_coefficient				
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	ABCP		alpha and beta-carotenes	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	ALKW	sea_water_alkalinity_per_unit_mass	total alkalinity	micromol/kg	SDN:P01::MDMAP014	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	ALKY	sea_water_alkalinity_expressed_as_mole_equivalent	total alkalinity	millimol/m3	SDN:P01::ALKYZZXX	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	ALTS	altitude	altitude	meter	SDN:P01::AHGTZZ01	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	AMON	mole_concentration_of_ammonium_in_sea_water	ammonium (nh4-n)	millimol/m3	SDN:P01::AMONZZXX	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	AMOW	moles_of_ammonium_per_unit_mass_in_sea_water	ammonium (nh4-n)	micromol/kg		

Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	AXAP		alloxanthin	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	BFUP		19'-butanoyloxyfucoxanthin	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CDOM	concentration_of_colored_dissolved_organic_matter_in_seawater_expressed_as_equivalent_mass_fraction_of_quinine_sulfate_dihydrate	colored dissolved organic matter	ppb	SDN:P01::FLUOCDOM	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CH1P		chlorophyll-a (less divinyl chlorophyll-a)	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CH1T		total chlorophyll	microgram/kg		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CH2P		chlorophyll-b (less divinyl chlorophyll-b)	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CHAD		divinyl chlorophyll-a	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CHAE		epimere chlorophyll-a	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CHBD		divinyl chlorophyll-b	milligram/m3		

Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CHC3		chlorophyll-c3	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CHCZ		chlorophyll-c1+c2	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CHLB		total chlorophyll-b	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CHLC		total chlorophyll-c	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CHLT	mass_concentration_of_chlorophyll_in_sea_water	total chlorophyll	milligram/m3	SDN:P01::CHLTVOLU	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CPH2		chlorophyll-a >2 micrometers	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CPH4		chlorophyll-a >10 micrometers	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CPHL	mass_concentration_of_chlorophyll_a_in_sea_water	total chlorophyll-a	milligram/m3	SDN:P01::CPHLZZXX	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	DAILY_RAIN		daily rainfall rate	millimeter/day		

Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	DEWT	dew_point_temperature	dew point temperature	degree_Celsius	SDN:P01::CDEWZZ01	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	DINW		number of dinophysis specimens in sea water	10+3/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	DOX1	volume_fraction_of_oxygen_in_sea_water	dissolved oxygen	ml/l	SDN:P01::DOXYZZXX	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	DOX2	moles_of_oxygen_per_unit_mass_in_sea_water	dissolved oxygen	micromol/kg	SDN:P01::DOXMZZXX	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	DOXY	mole_concentration_of_dissolved_molecular_oxygen_in_sea_water	dissolved oxygen	millimole/m3	SDN:P01::DOXYZZXX	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	DXAP		diadinoxanthin	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	FCO2	fugacity_of_carbon_dioxide_in_sea_water	co2 fugacity	microatmosphere		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	FLU3	fluorescence	fluorescence	FFU	SDN:P01::FLUOZZZZ	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	FLUO	fluorescence	fluorescence	relative unit	SDN:P01::FLUOZZZZ	

Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	FUCP		fucoxanthin	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	HFUP		19'-hexanoyloxyfucoxanthin	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	HOURLY_RAIN	rainfall_rate	hourly rainfall rate	millimeter/hour	SDN:P02::CPRP	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	NTAW	moles_of_nitrate_per_unit_ mass_in_sea_water	nitrate (no3-n)	micromol/kg	SDN:P01::MDMAP005	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	NTIW	moles_of_nitrite_per_unit_ mass_in_sea_water	nitrite (no2-n)	micromol/kg		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	NTRA	mole_concentration_of_nitrat e_in_sea_water	nitrate (no3-n)	Millimol/m3	SDN:P01::NTRAZZXX	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	NTRI	mole_concentration_of_nitrit e_in_sea_water	nitrite (no2-n)	millimol/m3	SDN:P01::NTRIZZXX	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	NTRZ	mole_concentration_of_nitrat e_and_nitrite_in_sea_water	nitrate + nitrite	Millimol/m3	SDN:P01::NTRZZZXX	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	NTZW	moles_of_nitrate_and_nitrite _per_unit_mass_in_sea_wat er	nitrate + nitrite	micromol/kg		

Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	OSAT	fractional_saturation_of_oxygen_in_sea_water	oxygen saturation	percent	SDN:P01::OXYSZZ01	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	PCO2	surface_partial_pressure_of_carbon_dioxide_in_sea_water	co2 partial pressure	microatmosphere	SDN:P01::PCO2XXXX	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	PERP		peridinin	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	PETD		daily potential evapotranspiration	millimeter/day	SDN:P01::POTEVAPT	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	PHE2		pheophytin >2 micrometers	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	PHE4		pheophytin >10 micrometers	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	PHEA		pheophytin-a	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	PHEB		pheophytin-b	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	PHEC		pheophytin-c	milligram/m3		

Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	PHOS	mole_concentration_of_phosphate_in_sea_water	phosphate (po4-p)	millimol/m3	SDN:P01::PHOSZZXX	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	PHOW	moles_of_phosphate_per_unit_mass_in_sea_water	phosphate (po4-p)	micromol/kg		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	PHPH	sea_water_ph_reported_on_total_scale	ph	none	SDN:P01::PHXXZZXX	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	PHTP		total pheophytin	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	PHYC		phycocyanin	milligram/m3	SDN:P01::PHYCSP4	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	PXAP		prasinoxanthin	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	SAMA		zeaxanthin	decibel		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	SECC	secchi_depth_of_sea_water	secchi disk depth	meter		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	SIGMA_THETA	sea_water_sigma_theta	sea sigma-theta	kg/m3	SDN:P01::SIGTPR01	

Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	SLCA	mole_concentration_of_silicate_in_sea_water	silicate (sio4-si)	millimol/m3	SDN:P01::SLCAZZXX	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	SLCW	moles_of_silicate_per_unit_mass_in_sea_water	silicate (sio4-si)	micromol/kg		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	SVEL	speed_of_sound_in_sea_water	sound velocity	meter/second	SDN:P01::SVELXXXX	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	TEMP_DOXY	temperature_of_sensor_for_oxygen_in_sea_water	sea temperature from oxygen sensor	degree_Celsius	SDN:P01::OXYTAAOP	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	TPAW		dissolved adenosine triphosphate	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	TPHP		total pheopigments	milligram/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	TSMP	mass_concentration_of_suspended_matter_in_sea_water	total suspended matter	gram/m3	SDN:P01::TSEDZZZZ	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	TUR4	sea_water_turbidity	turbidity	ntu	SDN:P01::TURBXXXX	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	TXAP		diatoxanthin	milligram/m3		

Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	UDOX		dissolved oxygen (deprecated)	unknown		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	REDS		reduction_potential	volt		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	TURMGL	sea_water_turbidity	turbidity	milligram/l	SDN:P02::TSED	
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CHLA_FLUORESCENCE		Chlorophyll-a fluorescence	mg/m3		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	COND_MEAN	sea_water_electrical_conduc tivity	Seawater conductivity	milliS cm-1		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	O2_RBR_CONC_MEAN	mole_concentration_of_disso lved_molecular_oxygen_in_s ea_water	Oxygen concentration RBR	micromol L-1		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	O2_RBR_SAT_MEAN	fractional_saturation_of_oxy gen_in_sea_water	Oxygen saturation RBR	%		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	O2_AANDERAA_CONC_UN COR_MEAN	mole_concentration_of_disso lved_molecular_oxygen_in_s ea_water	Oxygen concentration AANDERAA	micromol L-1		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	O2_AANDERAA_SAT_MEAN	fractional_saturation_of_oxy gen_in_sea_water	Oxygen saturation AANDERAA	%		

Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CHLOR_MEAN	mass_concentration_of_chlorophyll_in_sea_water	Chlorophyll concentration	microgram L-1		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	COND_RBR_MEAN	sea_water_electrical_conductivity	Seawater conductivity RBR	mS cm-1		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CHLOR_RBR_MEAN	mass_concentration_of_chlorophyll_in_sea_water	Chlorophyll concentration RBR	microgram L-1		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	DP1	dew_point_temperature	dew point temperature - port sensor	degree_Celsius		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	DP2	dew_point_temperature	dew point temperature - starboard sensor	degree_Celsius		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	PH25		Ph at 25 °C and 0 dbar	1		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	NGDW		Dissolved nitrogen	mmol/kg		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	NODW		Dissolved organic nitrogen	mmol/kg		
Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	TICW		Dissolved inorganic carbon	mmol/kg		

Water conductivity/ BioGeoChemical	CORW		Dissolved organic carbon	mmol/kg		
Waves	VDIR	sea_surface_wave_from_dire ction	wave direction rel. true north	degree	SDN:P01::GWRZZ01	
Waves	VAVT	sea_surface_wave_zero_upc rossing_period	aver. period highest 1/3 wave	second	SDN:P01::GTZHZZ01	
Waves	VAVH	sea_surface_wave_significan t_height	aver. height highest 1/3 wave	meter	SDN:P01::GAVHZZ01	
Waves	VCMX	sea_surface_wave_maximum _height	max crest trough wave height	meter	SDN:P01::GCMXZZ01	
Waves	VEPK	sea_surface_wave_energy_a t_variance_spectral_density_ maximum	wave spectrum peak energy	m2 second	SDN:P01::GEPKZZ01	
Waves	VHM0	sea_surface_wave_significan t_height	spectral signif. wave height	meter	SDN:P01::HMZEZZ01	
Waves	VPED	sea_surface_wave_from_dire ction_at_variance_spectral_d ensity_maximum	wave spectrum peak energy dir.	degree	SDN:P01::GPEZZ01	
Waves	VPSP	sea_surface_wave_directiona l_spread_at_variance_spectr al_density_maximum	dir. spreading at wave peak	degree	SDN:P01::GSPRZZ01	
Waves	VSMC		spect. moment(0,2) wave period	second	SDN:P01::GTZAMAZ2	
Waves	VTDH	sea_surface_wave_significan t_height	significant wave height	meter	SDN:P01::HSTKDP01	

Waves	VTPK	sea_surface_wave_period_at_variance_spectral_density_maximum	wave spectrum peak period	second	SDN:P01::GTPKZZ01	
Waves	VTZA	sea_surface_wave_zero_upcrossing_period	aver zero crossing wave period	second	SDN:P01::GTZAZZ01	
Waves	WVST		wave height and period statistics		SDN:P02::WVST	
Waves	VDEN	sea_surface_wave_variance_spectral_density				
Waves	SWDR		swell direction rel true n.	degree	SDN:P01::GDSWZZ01	
Waves	SWHT		swell height	meter	SDN:P01::GHSWZZ01	
Waves	SWPR		swell period	second	SDN:P01::GSZZXXXX	
Waves	VMAT		max period highest 1/3 wave	second	SDN:P02::WVST	
Waves	VTZM	sea_surface_wave_period_of_highest_wave	period of the highest wave	second		
Waves	WV_MAX_HGT		maximum wave height	meter		VEMH
Waves	WV_MAX_PER		maximum wave period	second		VTMX
Waves	WV_SIG_DIR		significant wave direction	degree		VDIR
Waves	WV_SIG_PER		significant wave period	second		VGTA
Waves	WV_GIG_PER		dominant/peak period	s		VGTA
Waves	VEMH	sea_surface_wave_maximum_height	Estimated maximum wave height	meter	SDN:P01::GCMXVS01	

Waves	VGHS	sea_surface_wave_significant_height	Generic significant wave height (Hs)	meter	SDN:P01::GTDHZZ01	
Waves	VGTA	sea_surface_wave_mean_period	Generic average wave period	second	SDN:P01::GTAMZZ01	
Waves	VH110	sea_surface_wave_mean_height_of_highest_tenth	Average height highest 1/10 wave (H1/10)	meter	SDN:P01::GTDZ01	
Waves	VHZA	sea_surface_wave_mean_height	Average zero crossing wave height (H _{zm})	meter	SDN:P01::HZAVZZ01	
Waves	VMDR	sea_surface_wave_from_direction	Mean wave direction from (Mdir)	degree	SDN:P01::GMWDZZ01	
Waves	VMNL	sea_surface_wave_maximum_trough_depth	Depth of the deepest trough	meter	SDN:P01:GMNLZZ01	
Waves	VMXL	sea_surface_wave_maximum_crest_height	Height of the highest crest	meter	SDN:P01:GMXLZZ01	
Waves	VST1	sea_surface_wave_maximum_steepness	Maximum wave steepness	1	SDN:P01::WVSTZZ01	
Waves	VT110	sea_surface_wave_mean_period_of_highest_tenth	Average period highest 1/10 wave (T1/10)	second	SDN:P01::GTZHTN01	
Waves	VTM02	sea_surface_wave_mean_period_from_variance_spectral_density_second_frequency_moment	Spectral moments (0,2) wave period (T _{m02})	second	SDN:P01::GTZAM2ZZ	
Waves	VTM10	sea_surface_wave_mean_period_from_variance_spectral_density_inverse_frequency_moment	Spectral moments (-1,0) wave period (T _{m-10})	second	SDN:P01::GTZAM1ZZ	

Waves	VTMX	sea_surface_wave_maximum_period	Maximum wave period (Tmax)	second	SDN:P01::GTZMZZ01	
Waves	VZMX	sea_surface_wave_maximum_height	Maximum zero crossing wave height (Hmax)	meter	SDN:P01::GZMXZZ01	
Winds	WDIR	wind_from_direction	wind from direction relative true north	degree	SDN:P01::EWDZZ01	
Winds	WVSP					
Winds	WSPD	wind_speed	horizontal wind speed	meter/second	SDN:P01::EWSBZZ01	
Winds	WSTR		wind stress and shear			
Winds	UWND	eastward_wind				
Winds	VWND	northward_wind				
Winds	GSPD	wind_speed_of_gust	gust wind speed	meter/second	SDN:P01::EGTSZZ01	
Winds	WBFO	beaufort_wind_force	beaufort wind force	none	SDN:P01::WMOCWFBF	
Winds	WETT	wet_bulb_temperature	air temperature in wet bulb	degree_Celsius	SDN:P01::CWETZZ01	
Winds	WSPE	eastward_wind	west-east wind component	meter/second	SDN:P01::ESEWZZXX	
Winds	WSPN	northward_wind	south-north wind component	meter/second	SDN:P01::ESNSZZXX	
Winds	WTODIR	wind_to_direction	wind to direction relative true north	degree	SDN:P02::EWSB	
Winds	UWND_MEAN	eastward_wind	Eastward wind speed	meter/second		
Winds	VWND_MEAN	northward_wind	Northward wind speed	meter/second		
Winds	WWND_MEAN	downward_air_velocity	Downward wind speed	meter/second		

Winds	GUST_WND_MEAN	wind_speed_of_gust	Wind gust speed	meter/second		
Winds	TW1	wet_bulb_temperature	air temperature in wet bulb - port sensor	degree_Celsius		
Winds	TW2	wet_bulb_temperature	air temperature in wet bulb - starboard sensor	degree_Celsius		
Winds	GDIR	wind_gust_from_direction	Gust wind from direction relative true north	degree		
River	RVFL	water_volume_transport_into_sea_water_from_rivers	river water flow	m3/second	SDN:P01::RFDSCH01	
Under water noise	SPL1	SPL at 63Hz 1/3 octave band	SPL at 63Hz 1/3 octave band	dB re 1µPa		
Under water noise	SPL2	SPL at 125Hz 1/3 octave band	SPL at 125Hz 1/3 octave band	dB re 1µPa		
Under water noise	SPL3	SPL at full band	SPL at full band	dB re 1µPa		
Under water noise	SPL	Sound Pressure Level (20s integration time)	Sound Pressure Level (20s integration time)	dB re 1µPa	SDN:P07::CFSN0310	
Under water noise	SPL4	SPL at 2kHz 1/3 octave band	SPL at 2kHz 1/3 octave band	dB re 1µPa		

Links

- <http://eurogoos.eu/data-management-exchange-quality-working-group-data-meg/>
- https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/products/web_services/vocab/
- <https://www.seadatanet.org/Metadata>
- <http://www.cfconventions.org>
- <http://www.marineinsitu.eu/about-us/>
- <https://www.pmel.noaa.gov/tao/drupal/disdel/>
- <https://dods.ndbc.noaa.gov/thredds/catalog/oceansites/DATA/catalog.html>
- <ftp://ftp.ifremer.fr/ifremer/gosudv3/>
- <https://www.ndbc.noaa.gov/>
- <http://ioos.us>
- <http://www.soos.aq>
- <http://imos.org.au/>
- <https://www.gloss-sealevel.org/>
- <http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/>
- <https://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/gloss/>
- <https://www.ices.dk/data/Pages/default.aspx>
- <https://www.sonel.org/-Sea-level-trends-.html>
- <https://www.pangaea.de/>
- <http://emso.eu/>
- <http://global-hfradar.org/>
- <https://www.oceangliders.org/>
- <https://www.ego-network.org/dokuwiki/doku.php>
- www.meop.net
- <http://www.icommops.org/sot/programmes.html#SOOP>
- <http://www.epsg.org/>
- <https://www.glodap.info/>
- <https://www.socat.info/>

References and readings

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Annex

1.1 European Sources and Providers

Table 4. European Sources and Providers

Country	Name of the Institution
Albania	UPT - Institute of GeoSciences, Energy, Water and Environment, Polytechnic University of Tirana - Albania
Belgium	DGO2 - Direction générale opérationnelle de la Mobilité et des Voies hydrauliques – Belgium
Belgium	RBINS - Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences, Operational Directorate Natural Environment (ex. MUMM) – Belgium
Bulgaria	IOBAS - Institute of Oceanology - Bulgarian Academy of Science - Bulgaria
Bulgaria	NGO - Sustainable Regional Development and Environmental Protection - Bulgaria
Croatia	IZOR - Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries - Croatia
Cyprus	UNY CYPRUS - Cyprus Oceanography Center - Cyprus
Denmark	Berring Data Collective
Denmark	DaMSA - Danish Maritime Safety Administration - Denmark
Denmark	DCA - Danish Coastal Authority, Ministry of Transport and Energy - Denmark
Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark
Denmark	DMIOS - Danish Meteorological Institute, Oceanographic Section - Denmark
Estonia	MSI - Marine Systems Institute - Estonia
Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland
Finland	SYKE - Finnish Environment Institute - Finland
France	AMPA - Agency Of Marine Protected Areas - France
France	CEFREM - Centre de Formation et de Recherche sur les Environnement Méditerranéens - France
France	CEREMA - Centre Etudes et Expertise sur les Risques Environnement Mobilité et Aménagement - France
France	CNRS - CNRS Center for Particle Physics of Marseilles (CPPM) - France
France	CNRS - Paris Institute of Earth Physics, Marine Geoscience Laboratory - France
France	COM CNRS - Center of Oceanology of Marseille - La Seyne Sur Mer - France
France	EAUF - Service public d'information sur l'eau - France
France	ENSTA - Ecole Nationale Supérieure des Techniques Avancées - France
France	EPOC - Environnements Et Paléoenvironnements Océaniques
France	IFREMER - Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer - France
France	INSU - Institut National des Sciences de l'Univers - France

France	IPEV - Institut polaire francais Paul-Emile Victor - France
France	IRD - L'Institut de recherche pour le développement - France
France	IUEM - Institut Universitaire Europeen de la Mer - France
France	LOCEAN - Laboratoire d'Océanographie et du Climat - France
France	LOV - Laboratoire Océanographique de Villefranche - France
France	LPO - Laboratory of Physical Oceanography - UMR 6523 CNRS, IFREMER, IRD, UBO - France
France	Meteo France - France
France	MIO - Mediterranean Institute of Oceanography - France
France	SBR - Station Biologique de Roscoff - France
France	SCHAPI - Service central d'hydrometeorologie et d'appui a la prevision des inondations - France
France	Shom - France
France	UBO - Laboratoire de Physique des Oceans, Universite de Bretagne Occidentale - France
France	Universite de Polynesie Francaise / Géosciences du Pacifique Sud GEPASUD
Germany	AWI - The Alfred Wegener Institute - Germany
Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany
Germany	FWERI - Federal Waterways Engineering and Research Institute - Germany
Germany	GEOMARK - Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel - Germany
Germany	HPA - Hamburg Port Authority - Germany
Germany	HZG - Helmholtz-Zentrum Geesthacht - Germany
Germany	IFM - Institute of Oceanography, University of Hamburg - Germany
Germany	KIELMS - University of Kiel Institute for Marine - Germany
Germany	PANGAEA - Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science
Germany	WSAL - Waterways and Shipping Authority Lübeck - Germany
Germany	WSAW - Waterways and Shipping Authority Wilhelmshaven (WSA-WIL) - Germany
Germany	WSOB - Waterways and Shipping Office Bremerhaven - Germany
Germany	WSOBR - Waterways and Shipping Office Bremen - Germany
Germany	WSOC - Waterways and Shipping Office Cuxhaven - Germany
Germany	WSOD - Waterways and Shipping Office Duisburg-Rhine - Germany
Germany	WSOE - Waterways and Shipping Board Emden - Germany
Germany	WSOS - Waterways and Shipping Office Stralsund
Germany	WSOT - Waterways and Shipping Office Toenning - Germany
Greece	HCMR - Hellenic Centre for Marine Research, Institute of Oceanography - Greece
Iceland	IRCA - Icelandic Road and Coastal Administration - Iceland
Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland

Ireland	NUIG - National University of Ireland - Galway - Ireland
Ireland	OPW - Office of Public Works of Ireland
Ireland	UCG - University College of Galway - Ireland
Italy	ARPAL - UNIGE - Azienda regionale per la protezione dell'ambiente ligure e Università Degli Studi Di Genova
Italy	CNR ISMAR - CNR Institute of Marine Science - Italy
Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy
Italy	JRC - Institute for Environment and Sustainability (IES) - Italy
Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy
Italy	OGS - Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - Divisione di Oceanografia - Italy
Italy	UNITU - Università degli Studi della Tuscia - Italy
Italy	UPA - CALYPSO - Dip. di Ingegneria Civile, Ambientale, Aerospaziale, dei Materiali, University of Palermo
Latvia	LEGMA - Latvian Environment, Geology and Meteorology Agency - Latvia
Malta	UOM - CALYPSO - Dept. of Geosciences, University of Malta - Malta
Netherlands	Deltares - Netherlands
Netherlands	KNMI - Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut - Netherlands
Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands
Norway	BCCR - Bjerknes Centre for Climate Research - Norway
Norway	CMR - Christian Michelsen Research - Norway
Norway	IMR - Institute of Marine Research - Norway
Norway	MetNo - Norwegian Meteorological Institute - Norway
Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway
Norway	NIVA - Norsk Institutt for Vannforskning - Norway
Norway	UNBER - University of Bergen - Norway
Poland	IMWMMB - Institute of Meteorology and Water Management - Poland
Poland	IOPAS - Institute of Oceanology of the Polish Academy of Sciences - Poland
Portugal	Confederación Hidrográfica del Ebro
Portugal	Confederación Hidrográfica del Guadalquivir
Portugal	APA - Agencia Portuguesa do Ambiente - Portugal
Portugal	DGDT - Direção-Geral do Território - Portugal
Portugal	IH - Instituto Hidrografico - Portugal
Portugal	MARETEC - Marine and Environmental Tecnology Center - Portugal
Portugal	UAC - Universidade dos Açores - Portugal
Romania	INFP - National institute for Earth Physics - Romania

Romania	NIMRD - National Institute for Marine Research and Development - Romania
Romania	NIRD - GeoEcoMar - Institutul National de Cercetare-Dezvoltare pentru Geologie si Geoecologie - Romania
Slovenia	ARSO - Slovenian Environment Agency - Slovenia
Slovenia	NIB - National Institute of Biology - Slovenia
Spain	BIZKAIKO FORU ALDUNDIA - DIPUTACIÓN FORAL DE BIZKAIA
Spain	Augas de Galicia, Xunta de Galicia
Spain	AZTI - Tecnalia, Headquarters Pasaia(Gipuzkoa)
Spain	CEAB – Centre d'Estudis Avançats de Blanes - Spain
Spain	Euskalmet- Basque Government - Spain
Spain	GIPUZKOAKO FORU ALDUNDIA - DIPUTACION FORAL DE GIPUZKOA
Spain	IEO - Spanish Oceanographic Institute - Spain
Spain	IEOB - IEO/ Balearic Islands Oceanographic Centre - Spain
Spain	INTECMAR - Consellería do Mar - Xunta de Galicia
Spain	Malaga University (UMA) - Applied Physics departament II - Spain
Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain
Spain	PLOCAN - Oceanic Platform of the Canary Islands - Spain
Spain	PTBAS - Petrobras - Spain
Spain	SOCIB - Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System
Spain	UPC - Universitat Politecnica de Catalunya - Spain
Spain	XG - Xunta Galicia - Spain
Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden
United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom
United Kingdom	NERC.BODC - Natural Environment Research Council British Oceanographic Data Centre - UK